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EFFECT OF LIQUIDITY ON THE CAPITAL STRUCTURE OF NEPALESE MANUFACTURING COMPANIES

Yuga Raj Bhattarai

Associate Professor , Patan Multiple Campus, Tribhuvan University
and
Ph.D. Scholar at Tribhuvan University, Nepal.

ABSTRACT

This study has examined the effect of liquidity on capital structure of Nepalese manufacturing companies. The descriptive and causal comparative research designs have been adopted for the study. The pooled data of 5 manufacturing companies for the period of 2008 to 2014 have been analyzed using regression model. The regression results reveal that liquidity (LR, CR, NWC) is significantly negatively associated with capital structure. The firm size is also significantly negatively related to capital structure in three models estimated. Growth and dividend have positive but statistically insignificant impact on capital structure. This study concludes that liquidity has significant impact on capital structure with controlling the effect of firm size. Larger size manufacturing companies in Nepal borrow less as compare to that of small size.

JEL Classification: C23, C88, G32, L60

Keywords: liquidity, capital structure, leverage, Nepal, financing, manufacturing firm

I. Introduction

The crucial decision that any company takes is that of capital structure because capital structure decision plays undeniable role in the success or failure of the firm. The choice of the long term financing mix is generally called the capital structure decision. It indicates the extent of financing risk in the firm and also determines the proportion of borrowed funds in financing firm's assets. It shows the ways in which a firm finances its assets. Thus, deciding how to finance a firm is very important not just to the managers of a firm but also to fund providers and owners (Ajao and Ema, 2012). Firm with significantly high level of debt may have problem in paying financing costs and are generally faced with the risk of bankruptcy. A liquid firm is one that pays all its obligations timely and can minimize the risk of bankruptcy.

Firms in their operations seek to maintain sufficient liquidity position for timely paying their short-term obligations and smooth functioning. Moreover, Williamson (1988) has argued that the optimal level of debt of the firm is limited by the liquidity of the assets and it depends on the average usage of the debt in the particular industry. In this scenario, a closer link may be expected between capital structure and liquidity. Likely, access to external funding is generally easier for liquid firms whose financial ratios correspond to the criteria of financial institutions (commercial banks).

Liquidity has been identified as one of the important predictors of capital structure in developed and emerging capital markets perspective. Olayinka (2011) has stated that the leverage and liquidity are positively correlated in the Nigerian perspective. Further, Sarlija and Hanc (2012) have jointly stated that there are statistically significant correlations between liquidity ratios and leverage ratios. According to Booth et al., (2001) and Bas et al., (2009) knowledge about capital structures has mostly been derived from data in developed economies that have many institutional similarities. There are differences in social and cultural issues and in the levels of economic development. Thus, there is the need to examine differently the determinants of capital structure for firms in developing economies. Specifically, this type of study is not found in Nepalese context. This study intends to examine the statistical relationship between liquidity and capital structure of manufacturing companies listed in the Nepal Stock Exchange. Hopefully, this study is another piece of the prudent effort to fill the gap in the finance literature.

The remainder of the study is outlined as follows- section two reviews literature, section three discusses the methodology, section four focuses on results and discussion, section five presents the conclusion and section six incorporates policy implications and research avenues.

II. Literature review

This study is to examine the effect of liquidity on the capital structure of Nepalese manufacturing companies. Some of the related empirical studies have been summarized as follows:

Sibilkov (2007) has investigated the effect of asset liquidity on capital structure. Using data from a broad sample of U.S. public companies, the author has found that leverage is

positively related to asset liquidity. Further the result from the analysis reveals that the relationship between asset liquidity and secured debt is positive, whereas the relationship between asset liquidity and unsecured debt is curvilinear. The author concludes that the costs of financial distress and inefficient liquidation are economically important and that affect capital structure decisions. In addition, the author asserts that the costs of managerial discretion increase with asset liquidity.

Lipson and Mortal (2009) have analyzed the effect of liquidity on the optimal capital structure among American organizations. They have examined relevant ratios in the U.S. public firms over 20 years. The authors conclude that the firms with more liquid equity prefer equity financing and lower level of leverage in comparison with other firms.

Anderson and Carverhill (2010) have analyzed the liquidity and capital structure. Results revealed that firm's policy toward liquid asset holding is closely connected to the question of the firm's capital structure. In particular, results show that higher levels of long-term debt will result in higher levels of liquid asset holding and a reduction in the optimal use of short-term debt. The value of the firm is rather insensitive to the long-term debt level outstanding. The reason is that by adapting its liquidity policy appropriately, the firm is able to balance its various contracting frictions in such a way as to achieve approximately the same value of the firm for a wide range of long-term debt levels.

Olayinka (2011) has examined the determinants of capital of 66 firms listed on the Nigerian stock Exchange during the period 1999-2007 using panel data. The results show that there is a negative relationship between leverage and growth opportunities, leverage and tangibility, but positively related to liquidity as well as size. This negative coefficient shows that growing firms use lower amount of debt financing. The results suggest that leverage is negatively correlated with profitability which is consistent with the pecking order theory. However, leverage and size are positively related. This finding supports the view of size as an inverse proxy for the probability of bankruptcy. Liquidity is positively correlated with leverage which is consistent with trade-off theory.

Sarlija and Harc (2012) have investigated the impact of liquidity on the capital structure of Croatian firms using a sample of 1058 Croatian firms. Pearson correlation results indicate that there are statistically significant correlations between liquidity ratios and leverage ratios.

There are also statistically significant correlations between leverage ratios and the structure of current assets. The relationship between liquidity ratios and the short-term leverage is stronger than between liquidity ratios and the long-term leverage. The authors conclude that the more liquid assets firms have, the less they are leveraged. Long-term-leveraged firms are more liquid.

Kajanathan and Achchuthan (2013) have analyzed liquidity and capital structure in the Sri Lanka Telecom Plc using data during period 2005 to 2011. Based on the results from separate models, all the ratios in the short term solvency as current, quick, and liquidity ratios have the significant impact on the debt to equity in the capital structure. The authors conclude that the decision making on the capital structure is highly depending on the liquidity management of the Sri Lanka Telecom Plc. The authors asserted that firm should focus on the liquidity management to take the decision on the capital structure.

Khalaj, Farsian and Karbalaee (2013) have investigated the linkage between liquidity and capital structure among the top 100 Malaysian public listed companies from 2006 to 2010 fiscal years. Based on the multiple regressions results the authors concluded that there is a significant relationship between two of three proposed liquidity ratios and leverage. They have asserted that Malaysian firms with more liquid stocks prefer equity to enjoy.

In order to conduct a new study in social science, the selection of study variables should be guided by past empirical evidences and some established theory. Thus, in view of past empirical evidences, this study considers that capital structure is influenced by liquidity with other covariates such as firm size, growth and dividend payment.

III. Methodology

The sample and data

The population of this study constitutes all the manufacturing companies listed in the Nepal Stock Exchange. The convenience sampling technique has been used for selecting the sample. The sample of this study consists of five manufacturing companies that have complete set of data from 2008 to 2014. The companies selected for sample are: Bottlers Nepal Limited, Nepal Bitumen & Barrel Udyog Limited, Nepal Lube Oil Limited, Bottlers Nepal (Terai) Limited and Unilever Nepal Limited. The secondary data needed for this study

have been collected from the published annual reports of the respective companies. The official websites of the selected companies have also been deeply reviewed to extract the latest information and changes of the investigated companies.

The model

Pooled data regression model has been used in the analysis. The technique of pooled data estimation takes care of the problem of heterogeneity in the 5 companies selected for the study. The econometric model employed in the study is given as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta X_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where: Y is the dependent variable; β_0 is constant; β is the coefficient of explanatory variables; X_{it} is the vector of explanatory variables; and ε_{it} is the error term (assumed to have zero mean and independent across the time period). By adopting the prescribed econometric model, particularly to this study, following models are thus developed for testing:

$$TDR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LR_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 GROW_{it} + \beta_4 DIV_{it} + e_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$TDR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CR_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 GROW_{it} + \beta_4 DIV_{it} + e_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$TDR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NWC_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 GROW_{it} + \beta_4 DIV_{it} + e_{it} \quad (3)$$

Where:

TDR_{it} = Total debt ratio (ratio of total debt to total assets) of firm i in year t

LR_{it} = Liquidity ratio of i^{th} firm in year t

CR_{it} = Current ratio of i^{th} firm in year t

NWC_{it} = Natural logarithm of net working capital of i^{th} firm in year t

$SIZE_{it}$ = Natural logarithm of total assets of i^{th} firm in year t

$GROW_{it}$ = Assets growth of i^{th} firm in year t

DIV_{it} = Natural logarithm of dividend of i^{th} firm in year t

B_0 = The intercept (constant)

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = The slope which represents the degree with which capital structure changes as the independent variable changes by one unit variable.

e_{it} = error component

Variable and hypothesis

Dependent variable

Capital structure is considered as the dependent variable in this study. Capital structure is usually measured by the following ratios: ratio of debt to total asset, long-term debt to total asset, equity to total asset, debt to the equity and equity to debt. In this study, debt to total assets ratio has been used as proxy of capital structure because it shows the financing risk per unit of assets of the firm. It indicates the proportion of a firm's total assets that was financed by borrowed capital. It is hypothesized that capital structure is influenced by the liquidity and other control variables like firm size, growth and dividend.

Independent variables

Liquidity

Liquidity, as an independent variable, is measured by three different proxies: liquidity ratio, current ratio and natural logarithm of net working capital. This study assumes that there is a close link between liquidity and capital structure. Moreover, both positive and negative relationship can be observed between liquidity and capital structure in the past empirical studies. Anderson (2002), Sibilkov (2007), and Sarlija and Harc (2012) have found a positive relationship between leverage and liquidity of the firm. Olayinka (2011) has also concluded that liquidity is positively correlated with leverage. However, Frieder and Martell (2006) find that higher liquidity is associated with lower leverage, as predicted by the trade-off model. Likewise, Lipson and Mortal (2010) discover that firms with more liquid equity carry less debt. Tarus, Nehemiah and Geoffrey (2014) conclude that liquidity is negatively and significantly related to capital structure. In the same manner, Morellec (2001), Lipson and Mortal (2009), Chakraborty (2010) and Udomsirikul et al. (2010) have also found negative association between liquidity and leverage. Based on the majority of the past empirical evidences, a negative relationship is expected between liquidity and capital structure.

H₁: Firm liquidity has significant negative effect on capital structure.

Firm size

In this study, the natural logarithm of assets is used as a proxy for firm size. The size of the firm may have significant relationship with capital structure because larger firms tend to have less volatile cash flows, easier access to the debt market, and need more debt to fully benefit from the tax shields. Likely, Warner (1977) suggests that leverage ratios might be related to firm size. Daskalakis and Psillaki (2008), Heyman et al. (2008) have provided the evidence of a positive relationship between firm size and capital structure and they conclude that trade-off theory is valid. The trade-off theory suggests a positive relationship between firm size and

capital structure, since larger firms are less likely to go bankrupt because larger firms tend to be more diversified. Similarly, Al-Sakran, (2001), Hovakimian et al. (2004), Kurshev and Strebulaev (2005), Ogbulu and Emeni (2012) provide empirical evidence on the positive relationship between firm size and capital structure. Moreover, Olderink (2013) argues that static trade-off theory illustrate that there exist a positive relationship between firm size and the debt-to-capital ratio whereas a negative relationship is assumed in the pecking-order theory. Nevertheless, Karadeniz et al. (2009) and Karadeniz et al (2011) have reported that firm size and debt ratio do not seem to share a significant relationship. Additionally, Tarus Nehemiah and Geoffrey (2014) find that firm size is positively correlated and but not significant on capital structure. In view of the majority of empirical evidences, firm size is expected to be positively related to capital structure.

H₂: Firm size has significant positive effect on capital structure

Growth

Myers (1977) shows that highly leveraged firms are more likely to pass up profitable investment opportunities; therefore, firms with higher future growth should use less debt and more equity financing to mitigate this agency problem. However, as noted by Titman and Wessels (1988) this relationship may be moderated for short term debt and may even be positive. Consistent with many other studies in the area, the assets growth is used as a proxy for growth.

H₃: Growth has significant negative effect on capital structure

Dividend

In this study natural logarithm of dividend has been used to proxy for dividends payment effect on capital structure choice. The coefficient of dividend (*DIV*) is expected to be negative and significant with capital structure (total debt/total assets).The negative relationship can be explained by the fact that banks prefer firms that pay low dividends. The inverse relation is also consistent with the view that debt holders impose stringent covenants on dividend constraints.

H₄: Dividend has significant negative effect on capital structure

The Table 1 gives a clear picture regarding the study independent variables and measurements and expected sign.

Table 1: Independent variables, measurement and expected sign

Variables	Measures	Symbols	Expected sign
Liquidity ratio	(Cash in hand+ cash at bank+ short-term Investment)/Current Liability	LR	–
	Current assets / Current liability	CR	–
	Natural logarithm net working capital	NWC	–
Firm size	Natural logarithm of assets	SIZE	+
Growth	Assets growth	GROW	–
Dividend	Natural logarithm of dividend	DIV	–

IV. Results and discussion

Descriptive statistics

The Table 2 reports descriptive statistics of single capital structure indicator (TDR) and three liquidity indicators which are: liquidity ratio, current ratio and net working capital as well as three control variables such as: firm size, growth and dividend. The result shows that the average value of the capital structure (TDR) is 0.831 indicating that during the period 2008 to 2014 on average, 83.10 percent of the total assets of sample manufacturing companies in Nepal are financed by debt capital. The result reveals that Nepalese manufacturing companies are in higher financial risk position because in average these companies use only 16.90 percent of total assets as equity funding for financing their assets.

**Table 2
Descriptive statistics (n=35)**

Variable	Scale	Percentiles						
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	25	50	75
TDR	Ratio	0.831	0.436	0.363	1.779	0.580	0.737	0.846
LR	Ratio	0.039	0.123	0.208	0.294	0.023	0.038	0.130
CR	Ratio	1.084	0.254	0.587	1.792	0.936	1.049	1.193
NWC	Ln	11.614	8.572	0.000	20.212	0.000	16.662	17.280
SIZE	Ln	20.462	0.954	18.982	22.035	19.553	20.773	21.122
Grow	Ratio	0.139	0.248	-0.185	1.179	0.000	0.096	0.257
DIV	Ln	13.943	7.328	0.000	20.366	14.333	17.378	18.730

Source: Annual report of sample companies and results are drawn from SPSS-16.

The standard deviation of the TDR is 0.436, which shows the lack of substantial variation. As reveals by the Table 2 the minimum current ratio is 0.587 and maximum current ratio is 1.792 and average current ratio is 1.084. All these evidences indicate the poor liquidity position of sample manufacturing companies in Nepal. The average growth rate of manufacturing

companies is 13.90 percent which indicates that Nepalese manufacturing companies expand their assets by 13.90 percent annually.

Correlation analysis

The correlation matrix of dependent and the independent variables is shown in Table 3. The tabulated results indicate that capital structure (TDR) is significantly negatively correlated with liquidity ratio, current ratio and firm size. It implies that large size manufacturing firm with sufficient liquidity position use less amount of debt capital in financing their assets. Moreover, net working capital, growth and dividend also have negative but insignificant relationship with capital structure. The correlation coefficient of liquidity indicators such as: between liquidity ratio and current ratio as well as between liquidity ratio and networking capital are found 0.949 and 0.825, meaning that these variables are highly correlated. Still, there is no evidence of multicollinearity because these variables are alternatively used in the regression model.

Table 3
Pearson correlations coefficient of variables (n = 35)

Variable	TDR	LR	CR	NWC	SIZE	Grow	DIV
TDR	1						
LR	-.381*	1					
CR	-.403*	.949**	1				
NWC	-.200	.825**	.750**	1			
SIZE	-.494**	-.213	-.057	-.250	1		
Grow	-.033	-.203	-.156	-.254	.353*	1	
DIV	-.245	-.058	.106	-.097	.634**	.221	1

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**.. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Annual report of sample companies and results are drawn from SPSS-16.

The rest of the variables have correlation coefficients less than 0.80, implying the absence of multicollinearity. Thus, there is no evidence of presence of multicollinearity among the independent variables.

Regression results

Table 4 presents the regression results of effect of liquidity on capital structure. The values of R^2 are .518, .467 and .377 in model 1, model 2 and model 3 respectively. Likely, the values of adjusted R^2 are .454, .396 and .294 in model 1, model 2 and model 3 respectively. These results indicate that overall explanatory power of the regression models is fair. The p-values

for F statistics in three models are significant at 1% level of significance, thus imply that the estimated models are fairly fitted well statistically.

Table 4
Effect of liquidity on capital structure

$$TDR_{it} = \beta + \beta_1 LR_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 GROW_{it} + \beta_4 DIV_{it} + e_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$TDR_{it} = \beta + \beta_1 CR_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 GROW_{it} + \beta_4 DIV_{it} + e_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$TDR_{it} = \beta + \beta_1 NWC_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 GROW_{it} + \beta_4 DIV_{it} + e_{it} \quad (3)$$

Variable	(Model: 1)			(Model: 2)			(Model: 3)		
	LIQ = LR			LIQ = CR			LIQ = NWC		
	Coefficients	Sig.	VIF	Coefficients	Sig.	VIF	Coefficients	Sig.	VIF
Constant	7.723	.000		7.939	.000		7.490	.000	
LIQ	-1.818	.001	1.080	-.776	.003	1.061	-.017	.034	1.111
SIZE	-.342	.000	1.880	-.316	.001	1.841	-.323	.001	1.884
Grow	.151	.534	1.165	.160	.531	1.168	.171	.540	1.182
DIV	.011	.281	1.690	.013	.215	1.732	.009	.431	1.684
	R ² =.518			R ² =.467			R ² =.377		
	Adj. R ² =.454			Adj. R ² =.396			Adj. R ² =.294		
	F = 8.064			F = 6.579			F =4.539		
	F (Sig.) =.000			F (Sig.) =.001			F (Sig.) =.005		

Source: Annual report of sample companies and results are drawn from SPSS-16.

As a test of the presence of multicollinearity among independent variables in three models, variance inflation factors (VIF) have been computed. The variance inflation factor (VIF) in three models shows a value less than 2 for each variable. The larger the value of VIF, the more troublesome or collinear the variables and as a rule of thumb a VIF greater than 10 is unacceptable (Gujarati, 2004). Thus, VIF less than 2 for each variable indicates the non-presence of multicollinearity. The independent variables chosen for the model are best suited for regression analysis.

As shown in Table 4 and Table 5, the results of three regression models indicate that, there is significant negative association between liquidity (LR, CR, NWC) and capital structure. The results imply that Nepalese manufacturing companies with sound liquidity position use less debt in their capital structure. The findings of this study is similar to the findings of Frieder

and Martell (2006), Lipson and Mortal (2010), Tarus, Nehemiah and Geoffrey (2014), Morellec (2001), Lipson and Mortal (2009), Chakraborty (2010) and Udomsirikul et al. (2010) where they have found negative association between liquidity and capital structure. However, the findings of this study is contradictory to the findings of Anderson (2002), Sibilkov (2007), Olayinka (2011) and Sarlija and Harc (2012) where they have found a positive relationship between leverage and liquidity of the firm.

Table 5
Relationship between expected sign and actual sign with significant level

Variables	Measures	Symbols	Expected sign	Actual sign	Level of significance
Liquidity ratio	(Cash in hand+ cash at bank+ short-term Investment)/Current Liability	LR	-	-	**
	Current assets / Current liability	CR	-	-	**
	Natural logarithm net working capital	NWC	-	-	*
Firm size	Natural logarithm of assets	SIZE	+	-	**
Growth	Assets growth	GROW	-	+	NS
Dividend	Natural logarithm of dividend	DIV	-	+	NS

*. Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

NS indicates not significant

The firm size as measured by natural logarithm of total assets is also significantly negatively associated with capital structure in three models estimated. The negative relationship indicates that large size manufacturing companies in Nepal use less debt in their capital structure. This finding is contrary to priori expectation because firm size was expected to have a positive relationship with capital structure. Moreover, this finding is contrary to

Daskalakis and Psillaki (2008), Heyman et al. (2008), Al-Sakran, (2001), Hovakimian et al. (2004), Kurshev and Strebulaev (2005), Ogbulu and Emeni (2012) where they have provided the evidence of a positive relationship between firm size and capital structure. But this finding is similar to pecking-order theory, whereas a negative relationship is assumed in the pecking-order theory.

As opposed to priori expectation, growth and dividend have positive but insignificant association with capital structure. Thus, these variables are not considered to have significant impact on capital structure of manufacturing firms in Nepal.

V. Conclusion

The objective of this study is to investigate the impact of liquidity on capital structure of manufacturing companies listed in Nepal Stock Exchange. The research design used in the study is descriptive and causal comparative research designs. Three regression models have been estimated using the pooled data of 5 manufacturing companies for the period of 2008 to 2014. The estimated regression models reveal that there is significant negative association between three measures of liquidity (LR, CR, NWC) and capital structure. The firm size, a control variable, is also significantly negatively associated with capital structure in three models estimated, meaning that large size manufacturing companies in Nepal use less debt in their capital structure. Other control variables such as: growth and dividend have positive but statistically insignificant impact on capital structure. The study rejects the hypothesis that Nepalese manufacturing companies having higher growth rate and paying sufficient dividend to their shareholders use less debt in their capital structure.

This study concludes that liquidity has significant impact on capital structure and large size manufacturing companies borrow less as compare to that of small size. As a whole, Nepalese manufacturing companies are in high leverage position and they have poor liquidity management.

VI. Policy Implications and Research Avenues

Based on the findings from the empirical analysis, the study offers the following recommendations through which they can work to improve liquidity management and to have an effective role in designing optimal capital structure.

The average current ratio of sample companies is nearest to 1.1 meaning that liquidity position of Nepalese manufacturing companies is very poor. Thus, it is suggested to maintain current assets at least two times of current liability in order to keep up sufficient liquidity.

Average value of the debt ratio is 83.10 percent which indicates that Nepalese manufacturing companies are in high leverage position. Thus it is recommended to increase ownership equity by issuing new common share.

Further, this study is also hoped to be useful to academicians as a source of knowledge for further research. The study is concentrated on only the data from five (5) manufacturing companies and thus, further study should be carried out on the topic including more samples for enhancing the quality of results.

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